

and treated with a solution of 2-isopropylaminoethyl bromide hydrobromide (1.8 g) in absolute ethanol (10 ml). The mixture was stirred and allowed to stand for 40 min. The product was filtered, washed several times with water followed by a little ethanol. It was crystallised from benzene-ethanol (3 : 1) to give dirty white needles (70%), m.p. 255° (Found : C, 42.89 ; H, 5.04 ; N, 10.13 ; S, 7.53. $C_{15}H_{20}IN_2OS$ requires : C, 43.18 ; H, 4.79 ; N, 10.07 ; S, 7.67%) ; ν_{max} (nujol) 3 210m, 1 720s, 1 620s, 1 520s, 1 260m, 825m and 760m cm^{-1} .

Similarly, other 2-(N-substituted-aminoethylthio)-3-alkyl-6-iodo-4(3H)-quinazolinones (2) were prepared. Their yields, melting points, colour of crystals, analytical data and characteristic ir bands are reported in Table 1.

2-Benzoylthio-3-methyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (3) : A solution of 2-thio-3-methyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone^{1,2} (1.5 g) in 10% alcoholic sodium hydroxide was stirred with benzoyl chloride (1.2 g) for 5–10 min. A white precipitate was obtained which was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to yield white fibrous needles (70%), m.p. 248° (Found : C, 65.10 ; H, 4.15 ; N, 9.21 ; S, 11.12. $C_{16}H_{18}N_2O_2S$ requires : C, 64.86 ; H, 4.05 ; N, 9.46 ; S, 10.81%) ; ν_{max} (nujol) 1 685s, 1 665m, 1 640m, 1 625s, 1 545s, 1 295s, 1 170m, 1 130m, 1 090m, 1 005m, 800m, 765s and 690m cm^{-1} .

Hydrolysis of 2-benzoylthio-3-methyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (3) : 6N Hydrochloric acid (15 ml) was added to a solution of 2-benzoylthio-3-methyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (2.2 g) in ethanol (30 ml) and heated under reflux for 4 h. Ethanol was then distilled off and the reaction mixture poured into ice-cold water. The product obtained as white needles was filtered and dried. Recrystallisation from ethanol gave pure 3-methyl-2,4(1H,3H)-quinazolinone (4 ; 1.5 g), m.p. 244° (lit.^{1,2} 244°) ; ν_{max} (nujol) 1 690s, 1 640m, 1 625s and 1 550s cm^{-1} .

1-Benzoyl-3-methyl-2-thio-2,4(1H,3H)-quinazolinone (5) : A mixture of N-benzoylanthranilic acid (2.0 g), methyl isothiocyanate (0.6 g) and absolute ethanol (10 ml) was heated under reflux on a water-bath for 4 h. On cooling, the solid product was filtered and triturated with 5% aqueous sodium bicarbonate followed by a little aqueous ethanol. The crude material was dissolved in 10% alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution, filtered and reprecipitated by addition of dilute hydrochloric acid. The product was again triturated with water and crystallised from ethanol to give white crystals (75%), m.p. 95° (Found : C, 64.72 ; H, 4.34 ; N, 9.32 ; S, 10.56. $C_{16}H_{18}N_2O_2S$ requires : C, 64.86 ; H, 4.05 ; N, 9.46 ; S, 10.81%) ; ν_{max} (nujol) 1 690s, 1 650s, 1 610m, 1 600s, 1 540s, 1 330m, 1 280m, 1 220s, 1 185m, 1 100m, 1 090m, 1 050s, 910s, 890s, 815s, 810m, 780m, 760s, 725m, 710m and 665m cm^{-1} . The ir spectrum of 5 was non-superimposable with that of 3 in the fingerprint region.

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Synthesis and Biological Activity of Thiazolo- and Phenylthiazolo-2-carboxamido-pyrazoline and -isoxazoline Derivatives

N. K. MANDAL, R. SINHA and K. P. BANERJEE*

P. G. Department of Chemistry, Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-812 007

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THIAZOLE derivatives in general are largely used as antifungal¹, antibacterial², antitumour³, anthelmintic⁴ and diuretic⁵ agents. Further, pyrazoline and isoxazoline derivatives⁶⁻⁹ have also been claimed as potential biologically active compounds. Hence, if a pyrazoline and isoxazoline moiety be

coupled with thiazole moiety, the resulting compounds would be expected to show biological activity. Considering all these factors, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise a few thiazolo- and 4-phenylthiazolo-2-carboxamido-pyrazoline and isoxazoline derivatives (Scheme 1) and test their biological activity.

2-Acetoacetamidothiazole and 2-acetoacetamido-4-phenylthiazole on condensation with aromatic aldehydes yielded the corresponding thiazolo- and 4-phenylthiazolo-2-carboxamido α,β -unsaturated ketones which on heating with hydrazine hydrate/phenylhydrazine and hydroxylamine hydrochloride gave the corresponding thiazolo- and 4-phenylthiazolo-2-carboxamido-pyrazoline and isoxazoline derivatives. The biological activity of some of the derivatives were tested.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer.

Acetoacetamidothiazole¹⁰ (1): A mixture of 2-aminothiazole (1 g) and ethyl acetoacetate (5 g) was heated at 145° for 1 h. After cooling, the colourless crystals of acetoacetamidothiazole that

separated out were filtered and crystallised from ethanol, (80%), m.p. 167°.

3-(Thiazolo-2-carboxamido)-4-aryl-but-3-en-2-one (2a-c): An intimate mixture of acetoacetamidothiazole (0.001 mol) and an aromatic aldehyde (0.001 mol) was fused for 0.25 h. The resulting mass was cooled, extracted with ethanol and crystallised from suitable solvents to yield 2a-c (Table 1).

Synthesis of N-acetyl-3-methyl-4-(thiazolo-2-carboxamido)-5-arylpyrazoline (3a-c): Each of 2a-c (0.005 mol) was separately refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (0.005 mol), glacial acetic acid (5 ml) and ethanol (30 ml) for 8 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated, cooled and poured into ice-water, when yellow solid separated. It was filtered washed with water and crystallised to yield 2a-c (Table 1).

N-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(thiazolo-2-carboxamido)-5-arylpyrazoline (4a-c): Each of 2a-c (0.005 mol) was separately refluxed with phenylhydrazine (0.005 mol), piperidine (1 ml) and ethanol (30 ml) for 9 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated, cooled and poured into acidified ice-cold water. The separated product was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from suitable solvents to yield 4a-c (Table 1).

3-Methyl-4-(thiazolo-2-carboxamido)-5-arylisoaxazoline (5a-c): Each of 2a-c (0.005 mol) was separately refluxed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.005 mol), ethanol (30 ml) and potassium hydroxide (0.005 mol) for 11 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated, cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The separated product was filtered, washed with water and crystallised to yield 5a-c (Table 1).

Biological screening of some pyrazoline and isoxazoline derivatives: Biological screening of some pyrazoline/isoxazoline derivatives was made by the reported method¹¹ and the results are given in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

Thiazolo- and 4-phenylthiazolo-2-carboxamido α,β -unsaturated ketones (2a-c) were prepared by fusing 2-acetoacetamidothiazole and 2-acetoacetamido-4-phenylthiazole with aromatic aldehydes. The structures of these compounds were established with the help of the spectral data and elemental analyses. Compounds 2a-c showed absorption bands at 3 420 (NH), 1 685 (conjugated carbonyl group), 1 630 (olefinic double bond), 1 350 (NO₂), 1 175 (C-S) and 3 400 cm⁻¹ (OH). Compounds 2a-c were heated separately with hydrazine hydrate in acetic acid to yield the pyrazolines (3a-c) via the initial formation of hydrazone derivatives which cyclised under experimental conditions. Compounds 4a-c were prepared by the interaction of 2a-c with phenylhydrazine via the initial formation of phenylhydrazone derivatives followed by cyclisation

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	Compd. no.	X	R	M.p. ^a °C	Colour	Yield %
1.	2a	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	217 ^a	Light yellow	52
2.	2b	H	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	179 ^b	White	65
3.	2c	H	4-OCH ₃ -3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	158 ^a	White	57
4.	2a	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	185 ^a	Yellow	66
5.	2b	C ₆ H ₅	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	196 ^b	Yellow	58
6.	2c	C ₆ H ₅	4-OCH ₃ -3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	133 ^d	Yellow	62
7.	3a	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	141 ^a	Light yellow	45
8.	3b	H	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	202 ^b	Yellow	85
9.	3c	H	4-OCH ₃ -3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	216 ^b	Yellow	62
10.	3a	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	201 ^c	Yellow	56
11.	3b	C ₆ H ₅	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	192 ^b	Yellow	40
12.	3c	C ₆ H ₅	4-OCH ₃ -3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	178 ^c	Yellow	81
13.	4a	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	191 ^d	Red	58
14.	4b	H	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	146 ^d	Yellow	70
15.	4c	H	4-OCH ₃ -3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	197 ^b	Yellow	55
16.	4a	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	196 ^a	Red	54
17.	4b	C ₆ H ₅	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	111 ^d	Red	69
18.	4c	C ₆ H ₅	4-OCH ₃ -3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	175 ^d	Yellow	65
19.	5a	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	300 ^a	Yellow	41
20.	5b	H	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	274 ^c	Red	46
21.	5c	H	4-OCH ₃ -3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	302 ^c	Red	45
22.	5a	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	156 ^d	Red	52
23.	5b	C ₆ H ₅	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	147 ^f	Yellow	71
24.	5c	C ₆ H ₅	4-OCH ₃ -3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	162 ^d	Yellow	67

* Solvent of crystallisation: ^a ethanol, ^b ethylacetate, ^c ethylacetate-petroleum ether, ^d benzene-petroleum ether, ^e chloroform-petroleum ether, ^f chloroform.

TABLE 2—BIOLOGICAL SCREENING OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	Compd. no.	X	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>Pseudo monas</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
1.	3a	H	+	-	-	+	-
2.	3b	H	-	+	+	-	-
3.	4a	H	+	-	-	+	-
4.	5a	H	-	+	-	-	-
5.	3a	C ₆ H ₅	+	-	-	+	-
6.	3b	C ₆ H ₅	-	+	+	-	-
7.	4b	C ₆ H ₅	+	+	-	-	-
8.	Tetracycline		++++	+++	+++	++++	+++

(-)=No inhibition, (+)=zone size 6-12 mm, (++)=12-18 mm, (+++)=18-24 mm, (++++)=24-30 mm, (+++++)=>30 mm.

under experimental conditions. The formation of these pyrazolines was confirmed by their positive Knorr's colour test^{1,2} which is a characteristic test for aryl pyrazolines. Compounds 3a-c and 4a-c showed characteristic ir absorption at 1 650 (C=O), 1 605 (C=N), 3 420 (NH), 1 350 (NO₂), 1 230 (C-N) and 3 400 cm⁻¹ (OH). Similarly, thiazolo- and 4-phenylthiazolo-2-carboxamido α,β-unsaturated ketones (2a-c) on separately refluxing with hydroxylamine hydrochloride yielded the corresponding isoxazoline derivatives (5a-c). The structures of isoxazoline derivatives were fully corroborated by ir spectra which showed absorption at 3 420 (NH), 3 400 (OH), 1 685 (C=O), 1 630 (C=N), 1 175 (C-S) and 1 350 cm⁻¹ (NO₂).

The biological activity of some representative compounds was initially tested and it was found that all the compounds exhibit some antibacterial activity against one or the other bacteria, but none of the compounds was found to possess any significant biological activity. The activity of the thiazolocarboxamidopyrazolines and phenylthiazolocarboxamidopyrazolines remains constant.

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Synthesis of 3-t-Butylimino-4-aryl/alkyl-5-aryl/alkylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines and their De-t-butylation into related 3-Imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines

N. K. KHANDELWAL, B. N. BERAD
and

M. G. PARANJPE*

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur-440 010

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RECENTLY, we have reported the synthesis of 3,5-diarylimino-4-aryl-1,2,4-dithiazolidines involving the interaction of *N*-aryl-*S*-chloroisoithiocarbamoyl chloride and 1,3-diarythiocarbamides¹. In this communication, we report the synthesis of certain *t*-butyl group containing 1,2,4-dithiazolidines and their debutylation with the help of concentrated hydrobromic acid and a mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid and hydrochloric acid (1 : 3).

Interaction of *N*-*tert*-butyl-*S*-chloroisoithiocarbamoyl chloride (1) and 1,3-di-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide (2a) was carried out in cold benzene medium for 36 h. During the reaction the evolution of hydrogen chloride was observed. After the removal of unreacted 2a, the filtrate was evaporated and the resultant semi-solid mass was triturated several times with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) to give a pale yellow solid, crystallised from benzene, m.p. 162°. The product was found to be non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. On thermal decomposition, smells of *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate and *tert*-butyl isothiocyanate were clearly detected. On reaction with boiling

alcoholic ammonical hydrogen sulphide of moderate concentration, it afforded 2a. On reaction with benzylamine in boiling ethanolic medium, 1-*p*-tolyl-3-benzylthiocarbamide, m.p. 124° and 1-*t*-butyl-3-benzylthiocarbamide, m.p. 96° were isolated. On reaction with ethanolic picric acid, a picrate, m.p. 183° was isolated. The infrared spectra of the product clearly indicated the presence of $\nu_{C=N}$ (1 580), ν_{C-S} (650), ν_{S-S} (560) and a band at 1 370 cm^{-1} due to *tert*-butyl group^{2,3}.

On the basis of all the above facts, the product with m.p. 162° has been assigned structure 3-*t*-butylimino-4-*p*-tolyl-5-*p*-tolylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (3a).

The reaction of 1 was found capable of extension to other 1,3-diaryl/alkyl-thiocarbamides (2b–e) and the corresponding 3b–e were isolated. However, 3b and 3c were isolated as solid hydrochlorides and crystallised from glacial acetic acid (Table 1).

TABLE 1—3-*t*-BUTYLIMINO-4-ARYL/ALKYLIMINO-1,2,4-DITHIAZOLIDINES (3)

Sl. no.	2 (g)	3 (Yield%)	M.p. °C	Analysis% :		Eq. wt.
				Found/(Calcd.)	N	
1.	2a (11.5)	3a (95.8)	162	10.85 (11.38)	16.89 (17.80)	—
2.	2b (10.0)	3b HCl (48.2)	141	11.05 (11.14)	16.18 (16.70)	380.0 (877.5)
3.	2c (11.0)	3c HCl (48.7)	226	10.42 (10.37)	15.18 (15.80)	409.0 (405.5)
4.	2d (10.0)	3d (51.5)	148	11.18 (11.38)	16.48 (17.91)	—
5.	2e (12.0)	3e (46.0)	147	10.75 (11.38)	16.95 (17.31)	—

* C, H analyses satisfactory in all cases.

To product 3a when refluxed with concentrated hydrobromic acid for 3 h went into solution with the evolution of *tert*-butyl bromide. The resultant clear solution on cooling afforded a new product, m.p. 253°. It was non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. On thermal decomposition, it gave the smell of *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate. When treated with ethanolic picric acid, it afforded a picrate⁴, m.p. 230°. The ir spectra of the product clearly indicated the presence of ν_{NH} (3 450), $\nu_{C=N}$ (1 650), ν_{C-N} (1 280) and ν_{C-S}